

NOTES

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Metal Complexes of Sulfur-Nitrogen Chelating Agents: Organotin(IV) Derivatives of Diethylaminomethyl Ester of 2-Amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic Acid

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METHYL ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid is found to be a good chelating agent for several metal ions forming six-membered chelates¹⁻⁶. In view of antifungal properties^{1, 8, 7-11} of both the ester and the organotin(IV) compounds, it was considered interesting to synthesize organotin(IV) derivatives of another ester, diethylaminomethyl ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid, $H_2NCCH_2CH_2CH_2CC(S)SCH_2N$

$$\begin{array}{c} | \\ (C_2H_5)_2(LH)_2 \end{array}$$

and examine the structural features as well as the biological activities of these organotin(IV) complexes.

Experimental

All manipulations were carried out under rigorous dry conditions. Solvents were dried by the standard techniques. Diethylaminomethyl ester

of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid was prepared by the literature method^{2, 12}. Monobutyltin trichloride (93°/10 mm), dibutyltin dichloride (153-156°/5 mm), tributyltin chloride (102°/0.5 mm), dimethyltin dichloride (185-190°/760 mm) and diphenyltin dichloride (93°/10 mm) were distilled before use. Dimethyltin(IV) diisopropoxide was prepared by the sodium isopropoxide method. Tin, sulfur and chlorine were estimated gravimetrically and nitrogen by Kjeldahl method. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in benzene. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer as neat and nujol mull in the range 4000-200 cm⁻¹. PMR spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

General method of preparation of the organotin(IV) complexes of diethylaminomethyl ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid: Organotin(IV) chlorides (Bu₃SnCl, Bu₂SnCl₂, BuSnCl₃ and Ph₂SnCl₂), diethylaminomethyl ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid and triethylamine (in appropriate molar ratios) were taken in THF (~60 ml) and the contents stirred at room temperature (~32°). Triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered out and the solvent removed *in vacuo*. The products (Table 1, Sl. No. 1 and 4-8) were crystallized from benzene-hexane and dried at 50°/0.1 mm/1 hr.

Preparation of the dimethyltin(IV) complexes: Dimethyltin(IV) diisopropoxide and diethylaminomethyl ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid taken in appropriate molar ratios in THF (~60 ml) were heated under reflux. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the products dried at 50°/0.1 mm/1 hr (Table 1, Sl. No. 2 and 3).

Results and Discussion

Tributyltin(IV), dibutyltin(IV), monobutyltin(IV) and diphenyltin(IV) derivatives [compounds (II-V)] of diethylamino-methyl ester of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-carbodithioic acid, (I), have been obtained by the reactions of the appropriate metal chlorides in the presence of triethylamine (Table 1, Sl. No. 4-8).

Since the dimethyltin(IV) analogue could not be obtained in pure state, corresponding diisopropoxide was used as the starting material. Dimethyltin(IV) isopropoxide reacted readily to give the desired product (Table 1, Sl. No. 2 and 3).

Organotin(IV) compounds synthesised are dark brown shining foamy crystalline solids except tributyltin(IV) and monobutyltin(IV) complexes which are brown distillable liquids. All compounds

TABLE 1—ORGANOTIN(IV) DERIVATIVES OF DIETHYLAMINOMETHYL ESTER OF 2-AMINO-1-CYCLOPENTENE-1-CARBODITHIOIC ACID

Sl. No.	Products* (nature)	m.p. or b.p./mm (°C)	Analysis %			
			Sn	S	N	Cl
1.	C ₂₂ H ₄₀ N ₂ S ₂ Sn (Dark brown low melting solid)	128-30/0.02	22.77	11.77	5.12	-
			(22.26)	(12.02)	(5.25)	-
2.	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S ₂ Sn (Dark brown foamy crystalline solid)	118-20 (d)	26.76	14.74	6.49	-
			(26.31)	(14.21)	(6.31)	-
3.	C ₂₄ H ₄₄ N ₂ S ₂ Sn (Dark brown foamy crystalline solid)	107-8 (d)	18.64	20.45	8.84	-
			(18.68)	(20.18)	(8.82)	-
4.	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ S ₂ Sn (Dark brown foamy crystalline solid)	81-83 (d)	16.37	17.91	7.49	-
			(16.50)	(17.82)	(7.78)	-
5.	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ S ₂ ClSn (Dark brown foamy crystalline solid)	107-10 (d)	23.94	12.27	5.59	6.70
			(23.20)	(12.53)	(5.48)	(6.93)
6.	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂ ClSn (Dark brown foamy crystalline solid)	116-18 (d)	21.93	11.31	5.20	6.56
			(21.52)	(11.62)	(5.08)	(6.48)
7.	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ S ₂ Sn (Dark brown foamy crystalline solid)	121-22 (d)	15.72	16.74	7.46	-
			(15.63)	(16.89)	(7.38)	-
8.	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂ Sn (Brown low melting solid)	110-15/0.4	23.80	13.65	5.65	14.78
			(24.22)	(13.00)	(5.72)	(14.46)

* Yield, 90-92% ; compounds are monomeric as determined cryoscopically ; d=decompose

* In sample cases, C and H analyses were checked (values in parentheses are the calculated ones),

Sl. No. 1, Found (%), C, 50.95 (51.78), H, 8.81 (8.70) and Sl. No. 4, Found (%), C, 51.10 (50.07), H, 7.68 (7.85).

are monomeric in nature as found cryoscopically in benzene except dimethyltin(IV) complexes whose poor solubility prevented the determination of their molecular weights.

In the infrared spectra of the diethylaminomethyl ester, the presence of a broad band of $\nu(\text{N-H})$ at 3245 cm^{-1} and the absence of $\nu(\text{S-H})$ band at 2550-2650 cm^{-1} region reveal the following delocalized structure for the ester². The absence of $\nu(\text{S-H})$ even in the solution spectra reveals the absence of the enolized form of the ligand.

The modes of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ which appear in I at 1265, 1155 cm^{-1} along with $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ³, and at 725 cm^{-1} , exhibit a negative spectral shift^{1,3,5,13} of the order of 15-20 cm^{-1} in all organotin(IV) derivatives, suggesting the bidentate nature of the ligand.

In all the organotin(IV) derivatives $\nu(\text{Sn-S})$ ¹⁴⁻¹⁹ absorptions can be seen at 385 ± 5 and 325 ± 5 cm^{-1} as two sharp weak bands. $\nu(\text{Sn-Cl})$ ²⁰⁻²² frequencies in diorganochlorotin(IV) and butyltin(IV) compounds appear in the region 300-350 cm^{-1} . The characteristic bands of $\nu_{as}(\text{Sn-C})$ at 590 and $\nu_s(\text{Sn-C})$ at 500 cm^{-1} in tributyltin(IV) compound, (II), suggest that all the three butyl groups are not in one plane^{23,24} revealing trigonal bipyramidal structures for them. In diorganotin(IV) derivatives the presence of more than one $\nu(\text{Sn-C})$ ²⁵ bands in

the region 580-600 and 500-515 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{as}(\text{Sn-C})$ and $\nu_s(\text{Sn-C})$ suggests a *cis*-octahedral geometry for the *bis*-complexes. The characteristic band of $\nu(\text{Ph-Sn})$ ²⁶ appears at 1070 cm^{-1} in diphenyltin(IV) complexes. In the case of mono-butyltin(IV) compounds $\nu_{as}(\text{Sn-C})$ and $\nu_s(\text{Sn-C})$ modes can be assigned at 595 and 535 cm^{-1} respectively²⁶.

PMR spectrum of the ligand² shows the following signals (in τ scale), SCH_2N (4.92, singlet), CH_3 (8.88, triplet) of the ethyl group, 3 and 5- CH_2 protons of the ring and CH_2 protons of ethyl group (6.8-7.5, multiplet), 4- CH_2 (8.16, quintet) and NH (4.19, broad signal). In all the organotin(IV) complexes 4- CH_2 proton signals remain at the same position while 3- and 5- CH_2 and SCH_2 protons undergo a slight upfield shift due to chelation^{1,4,5}.

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Experimental

Preparation of complexes: $M(NO_2-Bz)_2 \cdot nH_2O$ ($M = Co^{2+}, Ni^{2+}, Cu^{2+}, Zn^{2+}, Cd^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+} and $n=0$ but 2 in case of Ni^{2+}): An aqueous ethanolic solution of the metal acetate was treated with hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (1:2.5 molar ratio) and pH was raised to 7-8 by adding a few drops of dilute ammonia when the neutral complex separated. The product was digested on a steam bath for about half an hour, filtered, washed with ethanol and dried at $\sim 100^\circ$ in an air oven.

$M(NO_2-BzH)_2 X_2$, ($M = Cu^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+} and $X = Cl^-$ or Br^-): Methanolic (or acetone) solution of metal halide (0.005 mole in 50 ml) was treated with stoichiometric proportion of ligand dissolved in the same solvent. From resulting solution, the dihalo complexes separated gradually. The product was filtered, washed with cold methanol and dried in air. The determination of magnetic moment values, solid reflectance and ir spectra of the complexes were made as reported earlier^{2,3}.

Results and Discussion

The neutral bis ligated complexes $M(NO_2-Bz)_2 \cdot nH_2O$ are insoluble in water and organic solvents like methanol, ethanol, chloroform, acetone etc., indicating their polymeric nature. Excepting Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} , the dihalo or other acidic complexes of other common metals like $Ni^{2+}, Co^{2+}, Zn^{2+}, Fe^{2+}, Mn^{2+}, VO^{2+}$ etc. could not be isolated in solid state, similar to benzimidazole^{5,6} and alkyl benzimidazole^{7,8}, probably due to weak metal-ligand bonding caused by low electron density on imidazole nitrogen of NO_2-BzH molecule.

The dihalo complexes $M(NO_2-BzH)_2 X_2$ ($M = Cu^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+}) are slightly soluble in ethanol, dioxane, dinso and DMF. The molar conductance values of complexes in DMF solution are negligible (Λ_M 8-15 $mol^{-1} ohm^{-1} cm^2$) indicating the coordination of halogen atoms in these complexes.

Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes are diamagnetic and do not display electronic absorption band in the visible region. On the basis of stoichiometry, four coordinated tetrahedral structure is tentatively suggested for Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes since tetrahedral geometry is the more preferred geometry for these metal ions⁹.

The colour, magnetic moment value (μ_{eff} 4.71 B.M.) and reflectance spectrum of $Co(NO_2-Bz)_2$ decidedly indicate its pseudotetrahedral structure^{10,11}. A strong band at $18020 cm^{-1}$ is assigned ${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition and a shoulder at $18,850 cm^{-1}$ is due to splitting of ${}^4T_{1g}(P)$ term under the influence of spin-orbit coupling in tetrahedral field¹².

$Ni(NO_2-Bz)_2(H_2O)_2$ displays magnetic moment value, ca 2.96 B.M., similar to octahedral or distorted octahedral nickel(II) ions¹³. The diffused reflectance spectrum in the region 28,500-10,000 cm^{-1} exhibits a weak and broad band at

Complexes of 5-Nitrobenzimidazole with Some Metal Ions

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COMPLEXES of various transition metal ions with benzimidazole and substituted benzimidazoles have been reported¹⁻⁶. 5-Nitrobenzimidazole (NO_2-BzH) contains an electron withdrawing NO_2 group capable of reducing electron density at donor benzimidazole nitrogens through hyperconjugation. It is, therefore, expected that donor ability of benzimidazole nucleus will be affected appreciably. In

the present note, the preparation and characterisation of Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes with NO_2-BzH are reported. The effect of NO_2 substitution on donor ability of benzimidazole nucleus is also discussed.